

Original Research

Product Quality and Business Strategy Impact on Market Access for Tanzanian SMEs Under the African Growth and Opportunity Act

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Abstract

The topic of market access through favored products has drawn a lot of critical attention, particularly for Less Developed Countries (LDC). However, although the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) presents substantial market opportunities, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Sub-Saharan African countries (SSA), including Tanzania, have not fully capitalized on these prospects. With an emphasis on exporters in Arusha and Kilimanjaro, this study examined the impact of business strategies and product quality on market access for SMEs in Tanzania under AGOA. Using a cross-sectional research design and a mixed research approach, the study selected respondents using both stratified and purposive sampling procedures. The study employed various techniques in collecting data, including surveys, interviews, and documentary reviews. The analysis utilized both inferential and descriptive statistics, with multiple regression employed to evaluate the relationship between dependent and independent variables. The results of the study showed that market access for SMEs in Tanzania covered by the AGOA was positively and significantly impacted by product quality in terms of product storage, packaging, labeling, and business strategy implementation. Thus, it was determined that the most important factors in predicting Tanzanian SMEs' market access under AGOA are product quality and business strategy. Therefore, it was suggested that the government should establish an enabling environment to guarantee a favorable exporting business function for SMEs operating under AGOA.

Keywords: SMEs' Performance, Trade Preferences, SSA, Tanzania.

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Introduction

The problem of market access through favored products has drawn critical attention, particularly for Less Developed Countries (LDC). This is because there is strong evidence that, one of the main ways that goods and services from LDCs have entered into large and competitive markets in developed nations like the USA is through Trade Preferential Agreements (TPAs) (AGOA, 2023; Kassa and Coulibaly, 2019). Additionally, Van den Bossche (2005) noted that market preference or access is crucial for companies like SMEs looking to reach a wider customer base and acquire new clients in the global market (Kenton, 2024). A country or business that has market access can sell goods and services into a foreign market with fewer trade barriers. Despite all of these preferences, some researchers have shown that trade preference areas such as AGOA have mixed welfare effects on participating nations, with net gains mostly varying depending on whether trade is being created or diverted (Tadesse, 2024; Zenebe *et al.*, 2015). Thus, the necessity for a comprehensive understanding of how AGOA contributes to market access chances for LDC firms has been central to numerous scholarly investigations. However, developed nations have implemented various economic cooperation programs and TPAs to improve market accessibility for SMEs operating in LDCs. One example of such a trade agreement, which is practiced by many African nations, is the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) of the United States of America (USA) and Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) countries (Simon *et al.*, 2021; Dzidzornu, 2017).

The Act was designed to foster economic and investment growth in Africa by facilitating African exports to the United States through the reduction or elimination of tariffs on African products. It creates a unique opportunity for trade between the U.S. and Sub-Saharan African (SSA) nations by removing trade barriers. AGOA was established in 2000 to help SSA countries gain access to the U.S. market and enhance their economies (Williams, 2015). The Act is notable for its tariff eliminations and duty-free access to the U.S. market for qualifying SSA countries. This provision enables these nations to increase trade, stimulate economic growth, and attract investments, while also enhancing U.S. foreign exchange earnings through access to American markets (AGOA, 2023). As noted by Tadesse (2024), eligibility for AGOA participation is contingent upon each SSA country's progress in establishing a market-oriented economy, upholding the rule of law, fighting corruption, and implementing policies aimed at poverty reduction. The US president makes the decision each year to approve each SSA nation's eligibility to use AGOA preferences. Also, AGOA seeks to improve market access and possibilities between the United States and SSA nations, as well as to encourage greater trade, investment, and economic development. Additionally, it encourages market-oriented reforms and the rule of law in SSA nations.

However, PTAs like AGOA, which encourage SMEs to participate in the international market actively, are a good method to share the advantages of new technology and innovation, which in turn improves the welfare of businesses and countries (Tadesse, 2024; Kassa and Coulibaly, 2019). The expansion of more productive and efficient businesses was thought to have been made easier by the higher exports that followed better access to international markets like AGOA. Nonetheless, the research conducted by the OECD in 2017 highlighted that a significant challenge for small and medium-sized

enterprises (SMEs) in Asia-Pacific nations and Sub-Saharan Africa is finding ways to generate new business chances in both local and international markets. This requires overcoming different product quality requirements, certifications, and customs procedures by SMEs from SSA.

This paper aims to present an analysis of how product quality and business strategy influence market access to AGOA for Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Tanzania. Tanzania was chosen for this study due to its status as an active participant in the AGOA agreement, yet one that has not fully reaped its benefits. The research seeks to offer new perspectives on the challenges faced by Tanzanian SMEs in exporting to AGOA, to deepen the understanding of how product quality and strategic business practices can improve the competitiveness and performance of these enterprises.

Currently, 32 SSA countries are eligible for the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) preferential trade area, down from the 49 countries that initially benefited from this market (Congressional Research Service (CRS), 2024; Muller, 2018). This reduction follows President Biden's decision to revoke preference benefits for the Central African Republic, Niger, and Uganda, effective January 1, 2024, due to their failure to comply with the rule of law and human rights standards (CRS, 2024). These three nations now join thirteen others in SSA that are ineligible for the program's advantages. While it was anticipated that the remaining eligible African countries would continue to benefit from AGOA by accessing U.S. markets for both goods and services, the reality is that not all countries have reaped these benefits. Since AGOA's inception in 2000, the U.S. has imported \$791 billion worth of goods from eligible SSA countries, averaging \$37.7 billion annually from 2001 to 2021. Additionally, a report by AGOA (2023) indicated that U.S. imports under AGOA surged by 57% to \$9.4 billion in 2022, up from \$6 billion in 2021. The key products imported under AGOA included oil, apparel, footwear, wine, certain motor vehicle components, various agricultural products, steel, and chemicals. In 2023, the top five SSA exporters to the United States were South Africa (\$14.0 billion), Nigeria (\$5.7 billion), Ghana (\$1.7 billion), Angola (\$1.2 billion), and Côte d'Ivoire (\$948 million), collectively accounting for approximately 80% of SSA exports (USTR, 2024; AGOA, 2023). However, when compared to larger nations globally, the total exports from all AGOA-eligible African countries represented only 5% of the \$36.5 billion in apparel exports from China to the U.S. in 2023 (AGOA, 2023). To foster economic growth and alleviate poverty, the Act has expanded its benefits to support Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) across all eligible SSA countries.

The export trends discussed above strongly suggest that AGOA has significantly contributed to the growth of SME exports from eligible Sub-Saharan African (SSA) nations to the United States. Nevertheless, empirical research indicates that it remains complex and contentious to definitively link the rise in export volumes from SSA directly to AGOA trade preferences as the primary factor driving this increase (Tadesse, 2024; Kulu and Bentum-Ennin, 2023). Consequently, there is a pressing need for comprehensive empirical research, particularly through micro-level analysis, to accurately assess the impact of AGOA on the economies of SSA countries, with Tanzania serving as a specific case study.

Despite the potential market opportunities presented by AGOA, SMEs in Sub-Saharan African nations, including Tanzania, have not fully capitalized on these prospects. Research conducted by Mueller (2018), Seyoum (2017), and Asante *et al.* (2016) revealed that most Sub-Saharan African countries did not gain the expected benefits from AGOA, while the United States reaped economic advantages by broadening its trade zone and enhancing security. For instance, in 2023, U.S. exports to its top five African market destinations reached \$12.5 billion. Additionally, prior studies have shown that the benefits of AGOA vary significantly among countries, with some nations experiencing gains (Kassa and Coulibaly, 2019; Athey and Imbens, 2017) while others, particularly LDCs, landlocked developing countries, and those with special needs, have not benefited (Tadesse, 2024; Zenebe *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, research by Frazer and Van Biesebroeck (2010) indicated that South Africa, Kenya, Lesotho, Mauritius, Madagascar, Ethiopia, and Ghana have derived the most advantages from the preferential treatment under AGOA compared to their peers. This disparity suggests a lack of effective investment policies and trade facilitation strategies by governments in Sub-Saharan Africa, which hinders SMEs from accessing the market opportunities offered by AGOA. A study by Simon *et al.* (2021) further highlights that SMEs from Tanzania have not gained significantly from AGOA compared to other East African Community (EAC) member states like Kenya and Uganda. Between 2015 and 2019, Kenya and Uganda exported goods to the U.S. valued at \$169 million and \$601 million, respectively, while Tanzania's exports amounted to only \$121 million (Simon *et al.*, 2021). Empirical studies indicate notable variations in the AGOA impact across different sectors, with the apparel and textile industries experiencing the most significant effects (Tadesse, 2024; Kazimoto, 2014; Frazer and Van Biesebroeck, 2010).

However, some considerable government efforts from Tanzania have been made by the country to improve market access such as the execution of SME policy and business strategies, implementation of Tanzania National AGOA Strategy, awareness creation about AGOA by TANTRADE and establishment of one-stop centers in various customs (Simon *et al.* 2021; Kazimoto, 2014). Nevertheless, all these efforts resulted in a less significant increase in exports in terms of money and the number of SMEs participating in the AGOA market. For instance, in the year 2023, Tanzania's exports were only US\$192.5 million under AGOA while its neighboring countries in EAC notably Kenya exported US\$ 895.3 million in the same year (AGO, 2023). This could be the result of limited access to AGOA and the inability of Tanzania SMEs to compete in major markets like the USA. This also suggests that the government's efforts towards assisting Tanzanian SMEs to access this important market are not at the required pace. On the other hand, producers from the USA claim that imported products from SSA should be subject to sound labour, environmental, and product quality standards which are the technical trade barriers (AGO, 2023). These requirements compete with the intended goal for the establishment of the AGOA trade agreement of removal of trade barriers through tariff cancelations and duty-free access to the U.S.A market. In contrast, their counterpart producers in Africa assert that AGOA exports are dominated by primary goods in the extractive industries and low-skill services industries. Such a non-diversified sector focus undermines the ability of AfCFTA member nations to strengthen the capacity of SMEs to manufacture finished products.

Collier and Venables (2007) and Brenton & Hoppe (2006) discovered that AGOA did not significantly influence exports from Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) to the United States. Similarly, Kulu and Bentum-Ennin (2023) indicated that AGOA trade preferences have not led to an increase in exports from SSA nations. In contrast, Kassa and Coulibaly (2019) assert that SSA countries have benefited from AGOA. Overall, there is conflicting evidence regarding whether AGOA has assisted SSA countries, including Tanzania, in enhancing their exports, investments, and livelihoods. Most current research highlights the macro-level advantages of AGOA while overlooking its impact at the micro level, particularly concerning the performance of individual small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Least-Developed Countries (LDCs) (Tadesse, 2024; Wangwe and Sungula, 2020; Kassa and Coulibaly, 2019; Baccini, 2018; Kazimoto, 2014). The discrepancies in previous studies underscore the necessity for further research to identify the key barriers preventing eligible SSA countries, especially Tanzania, from fully accessing AGOA benefits. Therefore, this study aims to conduct a national-level investigation on this topic to provide accurate insights into addressing the existing contradictions. Consequently, the current study focuses on evaluating the economic impact of product quality and business strategy implementation on AGOA market access for SMEs in Tanzania.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework Review

The ability of a business or nation to sell goods and services in a foreign market is known as market access. Market access, as defined by Ribot and Peluso (2003) in their study of a Theory of Access, is the ability of a country or groups of people to acquire, manage, or sustain admission into business exchange ties and benefit from it. Although it is frequently negotiated for the benefit of both nations' businesses, freer trade may not always be the outcome. Access to markets can have a greater impact on a country's or company's ability to benefit economically than ownership of those markets (Gnizy et al., 2017; Ribot and Peluso, 2003; de Janvry *et al.*, 2001). Market access is often facilitated through trade agreements and trade promotion efforts such as AGOA and others. According to Kenton (2024) and WTO (2011), market access can be influenced by political and geopolitical factors that shape diplomatic relations between countries which involves addressing a wide range of factors including trade barriers, compliance with regulations and quality standards, and customs procedures. The degree of market access for business firms such as SMEs can be affected by the trade environment in which they operate. Among others, it includes factors such as free trade and investment agreements, WTO rules, export product identification, quality standards and certificates, and the transportation system (WTO, 2011; Runge *et al.* 2000).

As ways of facilitating market access for most of SMEs in LDCs, various Preferential Trade Agreements (PTAs) like AGOA were developed by developed countries over the last two decades. This substantial shift has ignited extensive discussions among researchers and policymakers regarding the justification for these preferential arrangements, as well as their determinants and effects on trade flows, economic growth, and the welfare of both member and non-member nations (Ruta, 2017). As noted by Bagwell and Staiger (2016) and Ruta (2017), there are currently 796 recorded trade

agreements, with 557 being active and 354 in force. For clarity, PTAs, as defined by Dür and Elsig (2015), are agreements that facilitate trade liberalization between two or more countries without extending these benefits to all nations. This definition aligns with the principles outlined in the New Economic Theory of free international trade, which advocates for the elimination of trade barriers affecting the exchange of goods and services across borders. Furthermore, research by Limao (2016) and the WTO (2011) has shown that PTAs serve as a primary mechanism for enhancing market access for SMEs and fostering regulatory innovation among businesses and countries. For instance, the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA), as a specific PTA, was created to incentivize and facilitate access of SMEs to the U.S. market for eligible Sub-Saharan African countries, particularly in the agricultural sector.

Economic theory and empirical evidence from the literature confirm that the primary aim of Preferential Trade Agreements (PTAs) like AGOA is to enhance exports by eliminating trade barriers between countries. This perspective is supported by Blanchard and Matschke (2015), who observed a 10% rise in U.S. foreign affiliate exports linked to a 4-percentage point increase in the rate of preferential duty-free trade under the AGOA. In a similar vein, Frazer and Biesebroeck (2010) analyzed the effects of AGOA before and after its implementation, revealing a statistically significant 13% increase in U.S. imports from SSA countries compared to the pre-AGOA period. The impact varied across sectors, with increases of 42% for apparel, 8% for agricultural products, 16.6% for minerals, 73.5% for petroleum, and 14.6% for manufactured goods. Furthermore, Seyoum and Abraham (2022) conducted a study on the effects of AGOA preferences on eligible SSA countries, finding a positive and statistically significant impact on total merchandise exports from these nations to the U.S. Collectively, these findings suggest that AGOA has effectively facilitated an increase in exports from beneficiary SSA countries to the U.S. Additionally, PTAs, including AGOA, are designed to create welfare benefits for participating nations through heightened production and exports. However, this potential can only be realized if PTAs enable individual firms to leverage economies of scale by providing access to a larger market for their products (Dür & Elsig, 2015).

In addition to these raised export trends from SSA to the USA through AGOA, still there is a growing concern among international business experts on allure benefits distribution among eligible countries and key reasons for some nations forsake to benefit from the compromise. Evidence from the usable empirical literature determines that benefits from PTAs like AGOA cannot be evenly shared by engaging countries (Tadesse, 2024; Kassa and Coulibaly, 2019). This note was more noticed by Gnizy and others. (2017) that SMEs from underdeveloped countries participated in exports to the USA were not enhanced evenly. Likewise, Kassa and Coulibaly (2019) found that non-oil output (that is farming and food products) was not helping as wanted from the favored trade agreement. Moreover, Nogue and Staatz (2003) while evaluating the impact of AGOA on the fitness of SSA, found that results on the book of exports were assorted and distinct across land sub-subsector accompanying brands like crops, nuts, and produce growing as well staple merchandise (Kassa and Coulibaly, 2019). Ghana, Kenya, and Od'Ivoire were stated to gain more benefits from agricultural and food merchandise exports than different nations from the Land of the Sahara. This implies that skill was an inconsistency in the share of benefits worked out by worthy AGOA nations from Africa. Likewise, Collier and Venables (2007) note the lack of important or consistent tumors across all subsectors

for fit nations in AGOA. Generally, practical judgments from the accessible studies on the impact and cause of AGOA were largely assorted (Tadesse, 2024; Osabohien and others, 2021; Gnizy and others., 2017). To this end, however, ascribing the noticed changes in the SMEs export flows to AGOA trade preferences as the basic cause still presents a challenge to researchers. So, a need for a precise conclusion on the AGOA benefits demands exact empirical reasoning ruling for additional procedure shifts like business approach exercise and commodity feature emphasizes that holding the SSA is critical.

The contingency theory of export performance states that a company's exceptional performance depends on its internal and external circumstances (Scott, 1981). Contingency theory is used by Robertson and Chetty (2000) to ascertain that a firm's export performance (EP) is directly correlated with the environment in which it works i.e. both the business and regulatory environment. This implies that good business strategies and regulatory frameworks can facilitate the performance of SMEs in terms of export volume. Using this approach, Gnizy et al. (2017) further demonstrated how internal and external environmental firm determinants influence export dispersion in SSA. The study by Simon et al. (2021) revealed that both local and international-related factors such as poor technology, Low quality of products, bureaucracy in accessing business permits, limited business information, and lack of capital to finance business were inhibiting Tanzanian SMEs from engaging in the AGOA market. According to Beleska-Spasova (2014), contingency theory works well for comprehending the idea of SMEs' export performance. Beleska-Spasova also suggests that the export performance of companies largely relies on how they are managed and their business strategies. This theory links various factors (internal and external) to the export success of companies. In this study, the theory of contingency was applied to illustrate how business strategies and product quality can influence the export performance of small and medium-sized enterprises through AGOA concerning export sales.

Currently, empirical research on the impact of AGOA has primarily focused on understanding the macro-level causal effects of eligibility for Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries on their exports to the United States. These studies have utilized various analytical methods, such as reduced-form equations, time series analysis, and comparative policy evaluations, to assess the incremental trade benefits resulting from AGOA in comparison to earlier initiatives like the Generalized System of Preferences (GSP) (Tadesse, 2024; Ruta, 2017). However, there is a notable scarcity of empirical studies examining the effects of AGOA on SME exports at the micro level, particularly in countries like Tanzania. This gap highlights the need for research to identify the factors that optimize preferential market access under AGOA for Tanzanian SMEs. Gaining insights into the micro-level impacts and determinants of AGOA access could significantly aid the government's initiatives aimed at enhancing the export performance of firms operating under AGOA in SSA. Additionally, the results may further support the arguments of the Contingency Theory regarding export performance, which posits that a firm's export success is influenced by both internal and external environmental factors (Gnizy *et al.*, 2017; Robertson and Chetty, 2000).

Empirical Review

Previous research has shown that AGOA offers a significant opportunity for countries to enhance their market access and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) by gaining more access to U.S. markets. For instance, a study conducted by Kassa and Coulibaly (2021) in the United States revealed that many AGOA-eligible countries experienced increases in their export activities. However, the outcomes varied significantly, with benefits primarily concentrated in the petroleum and mineral sectors. In contrast, the situation in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) has been different, as illustrated by the limited participation of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in countries like Tanzania. Osabohien *et al.* (2021) noted that the underrepresentation of SMEs in AGOA is linked to challenges such as inadequate compliance with international product quality standards (including packaging, storage, and labeling) and insufficient infrastructure. Additionally, Simon *et al.* (2021) highlighted several barriers in Tanzania, including technological deficiencies, poor infrastructure, restrictive business policies, limited access to capital and loans for SMEs, and lengthy bureaucratic processes for obtaining business permits and information, all of which hinder the potential benefits from AGOA by SMEs.

In a similar vein, Adetoso & Akinseluse (2016) discovered that AGOA had no discernible impact on the growth of SMEs in Benin and Togo. The results of the study showed that local businesses in developing nations were unable to fully utilize the AGOA's released potential due to a lack of government financing, insufficient physical infrastructure, and outdated technology. The majority of SSA nations implement AGOA rules and initiatives sporadically rather than actively (Mueller, 2018; Seyoum, 2017). On the other hand, the United States gains economic advantages by enlarging its trade and economic zone in addition to its security objectives (Tadesse, 2024; Asante *et al.*, 2016). This suggests that AGOA's original objectives of boosting trade, and investment and fostering equitable and sustainable economic growth in SSA may not be entirely met by 2025.

Similarly, Adetoso & Akinseluse (2016) in Benin and Togo found that AGOA had an immaterial influence on the development of SMEs. It was further revealed from study findings that inadequate government support in the form of capital to the local enterprises, poor physical infrastructure, and inadequate technology in developing countries deprived them of full exploitation of unleashed potential AGOA. The majority of SSA countries do not intently implement policies and strategies for AGOA but on an ad-hoc basis (Mueller, 2018; Seyoum, 2017). However, on the contrary, the USA benefits economically by expanding its economic and trade zone as well as security purposes (Tadesse, 2024; Asante *et al.*, 2016). This implies that the initial intended goals of AGOA for increasing investment; and promoting sustainable and inclusive economic growth in SSA will not be fully achieved by 2025 as expected before. Generally speaking, a variety of factors, such as disparities in business environments, conflicting interests, a lack of credit, internet access, capacity, government investment, production costs, and bottlenecks, could account for variations in how SMEs use AGOA benefits (WESGRO, 2024).

Although preferential trade area like AGOA is a crucial force behind inclusive, equitable, and sustainable development, its advantages have not been fully realized in SSA, according to Namsrai (2017) in Mongolia. However, there are significant differences in the outstanding advantages of AGOA among nations. Furthermore, whereas Abadie *et al.* (2016) discovered that, AGOA had no discernible effect on exports from SSA to the US, Athey and Imbens (2017) in Europe observed that AGOA had a favorable effect on exporting innovative items. Although the results of these studies were conflicting, one study asserts that PTAs greatly increased GDP and reduced poverty (Sitharam and Hoque, 2016). According to Gnizy *et al.* (2017), it was noted that, while SMEs from rich nations who participated in AGOA benefited from preferential trade, LDCs like Tanzania SMEs suffered the opposite effect. In a similar vein, Kassa and Coulibaly (2019) found that non-petroleum products were not benefiting as expected.

Furthermore, Msemo (2013) in Tanzania discovered that poor levels of knowledge and monetary limitations hinder SMEs' exportation under AGOA. Other often cited problems included the lack of financial institution capital assistance, the high cost of fuel, the unstable power supply, and the technological barrier (Yahya & Mutarubukwa, 2015). According to Simon *et al.* (2020), Tanzanian SMEs' access to the AGOA market is influenced by both domestic and foreign variables. Their study's conclusions showed that Tanzanian SMEs' participation in the AGOA market was significantly impacted by both internal and external variables. However, Wangwe and Sungula (2020) connected Tanzania's low participation to inadequate use of the preferential market for non-agricultural goods under AGOA between 2015 and 2019.

Research Methods

Research Design and Study Area

The research utilized a cross-sectional design to gather data from small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) owners at a single point in time, aiming to create a profile of these businesses, their operations, and the related impacts. The design was deemed suitable for meeting the study's objectives, particularly in evaluating the role of product quality and business strategies employed by SMEs in Tanzania. This design enabled a comprehensive understanding of how product quality and the implementation of business strategies influence market access for SMEs participating in the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) in Tanzania. Moreover, the cross-sectional approach has been used in many previous studies because it is budget-friendly and saves time (Mashenene *et al.*, 2024; Magasi *et al.*, 2020).

The research was conducted in the Kilimanjaro and Arusha regions found in the northern part of Tanzania, which is recognized for having many tourism-related small and medium-sized enterprises that participate in exporting through AGOA. Kilimanjaro and Arusha were selected because they are dynamic areas involved in export business to the AGOA market through the available SMEs that receive support from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and East Africa Cooperation and the Ministry of Industry and Trade with all necessary information about exporting and market opportunities. Nonetheless, their export success is not clearly shown even though there are expected benefits from AGOA markets. Furthermore, Kilimanjaro and Arusha have popular tourist spots like Mount

Kilimanjaro, Ngorongoro National Park, Tarangire, and nearby parks such as Serengeti and Manyara. These regions were anticipated to provide important insights into the benefits and number of exports supported by AGOA.

Sampling Procedures and Sample Size

The study used a mix of non-probability and probability sampling techniques. For non-probability sampling, purposeful sampling was utilized in selecting key informants and study area for a better insight into how product quality affects SMEs' access to AGOA markets. Key informants were picked from the Ministry of Industry and Trade, Tanzania Chamber of Commerce, Industry and Agriculture, Ministry of Foreign Affairs and East African Cooperation, Tanzania Exporter Association, and Tanzania Trade Development Authority (TANTRADE) to gather essential information for the research (Kothari, 2010). The intended study group included SME owners working in the business field and involved in clothing, textile crafts, leather products, footwear, and agro-processing items within the Arusha and Kilimanjaro regions. To ensure a comprehensive representative sample, a stratified sampling approach was utilized, where SMEs were classified according to the Tanzanian Trade policy (2013) to capture a broad variety of experiences related to SMEs' export performance. In this context, SMEs in both regions were divided into three categories (groups) of micro, small, and medium enterprises based on a list of 455 businesses from regional trade offices. By applying a random sampling method, 60 SME owners were chosen from each region (Arusha and Kilimanjaro), resulting in a total sample size of 120 (Table 1). The sample size of 120 was computed using Cochran's (1963) formula as presented in equation (1) below.

$$N = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where; N = Size of the population, n = Size of sample obtained e = estimated level of an error (5%).

Data Collection

Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires designed to gather detailed information regarding the effects of product quality and business strategy implementation. Additionally, the questionnaire captured demographic data about the SME owners, such as age, education, and working experiences. Before the implementation of the full study, a pilot test was conducted with some SMEs in Arusha to validate the reliability and clarity of the questionnaire, following established guidelines for instrument testing (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). Table 1 presents the sample distribution from the two regions.

Table 1. Sample distribution in the two regions

Name of region	Categories of SMEs	Total Population	No. of Selected SMEs	Total SM
Arusha	Micro Enterprises	70	20	60
	Small Enterprises	90	20	
	Medium Enterprises	85	20	
Kilimanjaro	Micro Enterprises	60	20	60
	Small Enterprises	80	20	
	Medium Enterprises	70	20	

Data Analysis Method

The study employed a mixed approach method in which both descriptive and inferential analysis were employed. To inform well the inferential analysis, the study first explored the descriptive analysis to offer qualitative information on the nature of SMEs and the owner’s education and experience regarding exportation to AGOA. On the other hand, the Ordinary Multiple regression model was used in assessing the contribution of product quality and business strategy implementation on the export performance of SMEs operating under the AGOA market in Tanzania. The use of the model was based on the nature of the dependent variable (Export performance) being continuous allowing us to easily quantify the results. The results from the analysis were critical in concluding the contribution of product quality and business strategy in enhancing market access and export performance among SMEs in Tanzania. However, to avoid biased estimates and results, the study tested all key assumptions of the model which included Normality, Linearity, Multicollinearity problem, and Autocorrelation tests. The results of these tests are presented in the finding and discussion section.

To detail the analysis, the study analysis was segmented based on the two determinants (product quality and business strategy), and equations for the Multiple Regression Model were presented for each factor. The two equations were expressed as stipulated below:

For product quality contribution to AGOA market access was expressed as:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \varepsilon_i \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where: Y= Export performance (exports volume); β_0 , β_1 , β_2 , and β_3 are coefficients estimated from the model, X1 = Packages quality, X2= Labeling quality and X3 = Quality of Storage facility.

For Business Strategy the equation was expressed as:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \varepsilon_i \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Whereby: Y= Export performance (Export volume); β_0 , β_1 , β_2 , and β_3 are coefficients estimated from the model, X1 = Business strategy formulation, X2 = Business strategy implementation, X3 = Business strategy monitoring and evaluation.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Results

The data presented in Table 2 indicates that a significant majority (68%) of the respondents were male, while a smaller proportion (32%) were female. This suggests that most SME owners are male. This finding aligns with Kumar's (2019) recommendations regarding the necessity of eliminating sample bias to ensure the reliability and validity of study results. In terms of age distribution, the results reveal that the largest group of respondents fell within the 38-47 age group, accounting for 38% of the total. Conversely, the 18-27 age group represented the smallest segment of the population. This suggests that the respondents were of an appropriate age to provide insightful information, thereby minimizing bias (Creswell and Poth, 2018).

Table 2. Demographic characteristics of respondents (n = 120)

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Male	85	68.0
Female	40	32.0
Age Category		
18-27	15	11.58
28-37	21	16.85
38-47	47	37.89
48 +	42	33.68
Educational levels		
Certificate	20	15.80
Diploma	29	23.20
Bachelor	42	37.83
Master	29	23.17
Work Experience		
0-2 years	14	11.2
3-5 years	26	20.8
6-10 years	38	30.4
11 years and above	47	37.2

Additionally, the study findings (Table 2) indicated that 38% of respondents possessed a bachelor's degree, while 23% held a diploma. Those with a master's degree comprised 23% of the respondents, and only 16% had a certificate. This distribution suggests that the majority of respondents were possessing with sound educational backgrounds, as 60% of them had at least a bachelor's degree. These findings are consistent with Palil's (2010) report, which noted that the majority of interviewed respondents held either a bachelor's or diploma-level education.

When it comes to experience, Table 2's findings also reveal that roughly 37% of respondents had 11 years or more of work experience, while 30.4% had 6–10 years. However, just 11.2% of respondents had 0–2 years of job experience, whereas 21% had 3-5 years. This data makes it clear that SMEs had a sufficient amount of experience in foreign trading, as more than 67% of the respondents had six (6) years or more of experience.

Inferential Results

Multicollinearity Assumption test

Before analysis, data were subjected to rigorous tests of the Multicollinearity problem. The multicollinearity assumption was tested using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value. According to Hair *et.al.* (2010), a multi-collinearity problem occurs when the value of VIF is above 10. Results (Table 3) of this study revealed that there was no multi-collinearity among the independent variables as indicated by Tolerance indexes ranging between 0.771 and 0.701 while VIF values were also less than the recommended value of 10 indicating that there is no multicollinearity between variables.

Table 3. Coefficients

Model	Collinierity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Business Strategy	0.879	1.138
Product Quality	0.691	1.448

Dependent Variable: AGOA Market Access

Autocorrelation Assumptions Testing

Durbin-Watson d test was used to test the autocorrelation that the residuals are not linearly auto-correlated. In this study, results indicated that the Durbin-Watson test was 2.121 indicating that the residuals were independent and there was no autocorrelation in the data. This ascertains that the chosen model and data were appropriate. Similarly, other assumptions like normality and linearity presented by the Pearson correlation coefficient indicate the existence of normality and thus the results justifying that data were normally distributed (Goodwin & Leech, 2006). Studies by Goodwin & Leech (2006) and Curran & Finch (1996) demonstrate that serious problems of non-normality may exist when univariate skewness is ≥ 2.0 and kurtosis is ≥ 7.0 .

Effect of Product Quality on Market Access for SMEs from AGOA

Results in Table 4 show that, the adjusted R^2 was 77% which implies that the independent variable predicts the dependent variable by 77 percent. Similarly, all independent variables yielded a positive and significant effect on SMEs' performance in Tanzania. The high value of R^2 justifies the fitness of the model and the included variables.

Table 4. The Effect of Product Quality on Market Access for SMEs from AGOA

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	0.068	0.073		0.935	0.352
Product Package	0.285	0.093	0.293	3.063	0.003
Product Labelling	0.323	0.122	0.295	2.660	0.009
Product Storage	0.360	0.147	0.329	2.439	0.016
Dependent Variable: Export performance					
Adjusted R squared = 0.77					

Results as appendixes in Table 4 on package quality indicated a positive and statistically significant relationship with the SMEs' performance having a 0.295 coefficient. This implies that a unit change in the quality improvement for product packages as stated in AGOA product preferential resulted in increased market access in terms of export volume for Tanzanian SMEs by 30 percent. The findings fulfill the requirement of the AGOA product Law that, products being imported into the US from an AGOA beneficiary country would only be eligible for duty-free entry under AGOA if they've met the principles of product description standards (WESGRO, 2024).

Moreover, the positive relationship between the quality of packaging and exports as presented in Table 3, indicates the potentials that AGOA have for the SMEs' performance in Tanzania and other countries from SSA. However, these potentials could only be exploited by SMEs if the governments of eligible countries improve the investment and business environments which enables more establishment of packaging industries. This argument was confirmed by Signe (2023) that, Companies that have invested in product quality improvement to meet international standards have benefited from the U.S. market.

The findings of this study align with those of Wangwe and Sungula (2020) in Tanzania, who established a connection between product packaging and market access under AGOA for various agricultural products, including meat, dairy, sugar, chocolate, peanuts, prepared foods, and tobacco, revealing a significant relationship. Additionally, these results support the export performance theory, which emphasizes the importance of management efficiency in both internal and external factors as key determinants for SMEs performance (Gnizy *et al.*, 2017; Beleska-Spasova, 2014). Internal factors in these studies pertain to how SME management designs and oversees product packaging and storage. Furthermore, these findings are consistent with the research conducted by Osabohien *et al.* (2021) in SSA countries, which indicated that the inability of SMEs to fully leverage AGOA benefits stemmed from inadequate compliance with international product packaging and standards.

Regarding product storage facilities, the results as presented in Table 4 indicate that an improvement in the quality of storage facilities could lead to a 29% increase in AGOA market access for SMEs in Tanzania. This outcome underscores the necessity for the government to ensure that local SMEs utilize upgraded storage facilities to prevent

product damage during transit. These findings are consistent with observations made by Gnizy *et al.* (2017), who, through the application of export performance theory, confirmed that product storage facilities significantly and positively influence market access for AGOA products. Moreover, the results are in agreement with the Contingency Theory of Export Performance, which posits that a firm's export performance is directly influenced by the context in which it operates, including both internal and external environmental factors that can impact export outcomes.

The findings of this study align with those of Wangwe and Sungula (2020) in Tanzania, who established a connection between product packaging and market access under AGOA for various agricultural goods, including meat, dairy, sugar, chocolate, peanuts, prepared foods, and tobacco, revealing a significant relationship. Additionally, the results support the export performance theory, which emphasizes the importance of management efficiency in both internal and external factors as key determinants for SMEs (Gnizy *et al.*, 2017; Beleska-Spasova, 2014). Internal factors in these studies pertain to how SME management designs and oversees product packaging and storage. Moreover, these findings are consistent with the research conducted by Osabohien *et al.* (2021) in SSA countries, which indicated that the inability of SMEs to fully leverage AGOA benefits stemmed from inadequate compliance with international product packaging and standards.

Concerning the product storage facility, the data presented in Table 4 indicates that an improvement in the quality of storage facilities could result in a 29% increase in AGOA market access for SMEs in Tanzania. This finding underscores the necessity for the government to ensure that local SMEs utilize upgraded storage facilities to prevent product damage during transit. These results are consistent with the observations made by Gnizy *et al.* (2017), who, through the application of Export Performance (EP) theory, confirmed that product storage facilities have a significant and positive impact on the market access of AGOA products. Furthermore, the findings are by the principles of the Contingency Theory of Export Performance, which posits that a firm's export performance is closely linked to the specific context in which it operates, encompassing both internal and external environmental factors that can influence export outcomes.

In a similar vein, SMEs in Tanzania indicated that a properly labeled package improved their ability to access markets under AGOA. This suggests that the volume of sales from SMEs could rise by 32% for each unit of improvement in the product labeling exported under AGOA. This is because one of the AGOA's requirements is that products be clearly and properly labeled as per the product quality requirement standard. The results of the study support those of Coulibaly and Kassa (2022) in Togo, who connected product labeling to the AGOA agricultural product market. This suggests that using advanced technology to design product labels increases a product's efficiency and competitiveness in the AGOA market. To support these conclusions, Simon *et al.* (2021) found that the performance of Tanzanian SMEs operating under AGOA preference was significantly impacted by both internal and external factors, including labeling quality.

On the other hand, study results (Table 4) on SMEs in Tanzania indicated that a properly labeled package improved positively their ability to access AGOA markets. This suggests that the volume of sales from SMEs could rise by 32% for each unit of

improvement in the product labeling exported under AGOA. This is because one of the AGOA's requirements is that products be clearly and properly labeled per the product quality requirement standard. The results of the study support those of Kassa (2021) in Woldia City, who connected product labeling to the AGOA agricultural product market.

Effect of Country's Business Strategies on Market Access for SMEs from AGOA

Table 5 displays the results of the regression analysis, revealing that the adjusted R² for the overall model stands at 77%. This indicates that the independent variables related to business strategy formulation, implementation, and monitoring and evaluation effectively predict market access for Tanzanian licensed products under AGOA. Consequently, these independent variables significantly influence export performance, which serves as a measure of market access for AGOA-licensed products in Tanzania.

Additionally, all variables analyzed in the model demonstrated a significant positive correlation with the performance of SMEs. This suggests that if the country effectively formulates and implements business strategies that support SMEs' access to AGOA, these enterprises are likely to thrive and increase their exports to the U.S. market.

Table 5. Effects of Business Strategies on Export Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	0.066	0.074		0.893	0.374
Business Strategy Formulation	0.333	0.091	0.343	3.663	0.000
Business Strategy Implementation	0.291	0.114	0.266	2.560	0.012
Business Strategy Monitoring and Evaluation	0.339	0.124	0.310	2.736	0.007
Dependent Variable: Export Performance Adjusted R squared = 0.77					

Results (in Table 5) demonstrate that having clear processes for developing business strategies is crucial and has a statistically significant beneficial impact on increasing the amount of exports for Tanzanian SMEs operating under AGOA. This suggests that a well-thought-out company plan could result in a 34% increase in product market access in the AGOA market. This result was consistent with that of Seyoum and Abraham (2022), who found that AGOA significantly increased the number of items sent to the US from SSA nations, especially manufactured and agricultural goods that were granted duty-free access. Additionally, they are more in line with research conducted in Woldia by Kassa (2021), who found that developing a business plan is essential to enhancing AGOA's market access for SSA-licensed goods. Therefore, adopting precisely the well-stated business strategy lays the way for the active engagement of SMEs in PTAs. Moreover, a well-formulated business strategy will help companies deal with market access issues in the appropriate way and at the appropriate time.

Similarly, the implementation of the business strategy presented statistically significant and positive effects on the exports of SMEs with a coefficient of 0.266 (Table 5). The coefficient indicates that, if the formulated business strategy is well implemented as planned could lead to 27% increase in the market access for products under the AGOA market. Moreover, if a sound business strategy is well implemented by the eligible country will set the future success of the business and provide a road map toward accessing the AGOA market. Currently, Tanzania is implementing the business strategy known as the “Tanzania National AGOA Strategy” established in 2016 which focuses on four strategic subsectors for rapid and increased participation of the country in the AGOA market. The four key areas included garments and textiles, the agro-processing industry, leather goods and footwear and the last is handicraft which includes home decoration and accessories (Simon *et al.*, 2021; Tanzania National AGOA Strategy, 2016). Similar to these findings, Signe (2023) reported that all countries that adopted and implemented well a national AGOA business strategy experienced success in their exports to the US market by 90 percent. On the contrary, the empirical evidence suggests that the impacts of AGOA have been narrowly concentrated in a few sectors (e.g., apparel), and the positive effects on trade and jobs also appear temporary rather than sustained (Tadesse, 2024).

Also, the study findings are consistent with those of Simon *et al.* (2021) who noted that business strategy formulation plays a vital role in promoting market access of AGOA for licensed products from Tanzania. Additionally, the findings are in harmony with the Theory of Export Performance (EP) which states that the firms’ export performance (EP) is directly related to the business context in which the firm operates including the country policy and business strategy. This is because business strategy implementation is thought to define terms and techniques of business undertakings for the entire country about the market access of products licensed under the AGOA market.

Study findings underscore the critical role of timely monitoring and evaluation of business strategies in ensuring the effective implementation of plans aimed at enhancing SMEs' export capabilities through AGOA. The analysis indicates that appropriate and prompt monitoring and evaluation can boost the market access of SMEs' products under the AGOA framework by as much as 31 percent. This suggests that effective oversight of business strategies is essential for improving market access for AGOA-licensed products, as it simplifies participation for SMEs. These findings align with the research conducted by Simon *et al.* (2021), which emphasized the significance of business strategy monitoring and evaluation in influencing market access for AGOA-eligible products from SMEs. Generally, timely monitoring and evaluation of business strategies facilitate the control of their implementation, helping organizations achieve their set goals, which in turn enhances market access for AGOA-licensed products in Tanzania. This is consistent with Tadesse's (2024) observations that AGOA has notably increased total merchandise exports for eligible sub-Saharan African countries, particularly in sectors such as apparel, textiles, and light manufacturing. However, the impact on trade has varied among countries, with some sub-Saharan African nations experiencing greater benefits than others.

Conclusion, Policy Recommendations, and Limitations

Conclusion

This study assessed how business strategy and product quality contributed to SMEs' export promotion under AGOA. The results show that SMEs' business strategy and product quality favorably and significantly impact their ability to access markets under AGOA. This implies that as it makes participation easier for SMEs, efficient management of business plans and product quality is crucial for enhancing market access for AGOA-licensed goods. As a result, to get access to AGOA markets, SMEs and the government should focus their efforts on improving packaging and storage facilities. The results also provide a fresh view of the difficulties that Tanzanian SMEs face when exporting products and services to AGOA, offering a deeper insight into how product quality and strategic business methods can boost the competitiveness and success of these businesses. In conclusion, superior products and a well-executed business plan predict market accessibility through increased export volumes from SMEs involved in the AGOA market.

Policy Recommendations and Implications

The results of this research have both policy and practical significance for the government, decision-makers, small business owners, and investors. The study highlighted the decision-making information for all participants across the supply chain particularly in the AGOA market, especially in LDCs. The proper and effective use of these results will assist decision-making bodies and business regulators such as TBS and SIDO to enhance the business environment and the rules regarding AGOA market access qualifications. Furthermore, it adds to and supports findings from previous research and enriches the knowledge concerning the effects and factors influencing AGOA eligibility for SSA. Given these results, the researcher recommends that the government and other business sector partners ensure that favorable conditions for business and investment are created to support the production of high-quality products (like labeling, packaging, and storage). Additionally, the Ministry of Industry and Trade, working with the Tanzania Bureau of Standards (TBS) and Small Industries Development Tanzania (SIDO), should ensure that export-focused SMEs produce goods that align with AGOA's quality standards.

Study Limitations and Future Research

However, there certain limitations to this study that opened the door for more investigation. The first restriction stems from the use of primary data to estimate how business strategy and product quality affect AGOA market access. As a result, it is advised that research use a time series with a longitudinal design that spans a considerable amount of time. Both immediate and long-term effects will result from this, which may allow the government to have more say in long-term corporate strategies and policies. Additionally, we evaluated the effects of product quality and business strategy by deploying SMEs in just two regions as a case study; therefore, we recommend that future research encompass a wider range of regions in the nation.

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